

Evaluation of antibacterial activity of *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* spp.

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ABSTRACT

Bacteria have known as one of the main important limitation factors of many agricultural products. The purpose of the present study was to evaluate the antibacterial activities of different species of *Penicillium* and *Aspergillus* on some important bacteria. For this intention 12 and 21 species of *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium*, were applied, respectively. Gram-negative bacteria conducted in this research were *Pseudomonas viridiflava*, *Xanthomonas campestris* sp. *Campestris* and *Escherichia coli* and the only gram-positive bacterium was *Rhizobacter iranicus*. Fungal and bacterial isolates were dual cultured simultaneously on Potato Dextrose Broth (PDB) and were shaken with 120 rpm. The samples were investigated after a week. The results of this study demonstrated that none of fungal species could inhibit *E. coli* and the most of the studied species couldn't suppress the growth of *P. viridiflava* except isolates of (5033, 5037, and 5071) from *P. chrysogenum*. On the other hand, *A. awamori*, *A. ferreus*, *A. ostiatus*, *A. niger*, *A. foetidus*, *P. mali*, *P. crustaceum* and *P. citrinum* could lead to inhibition of *X. campestris* sp. *campestris* Gram positive bacterium, *Rhizobacter iranicus*, was not able to grow in the presence of all species of *Aspergillus*. On the contrary, species of *P. piscarium*, *P. corylophilum*, *P. griseofulvum* and *P. chrysogenum* couldn't prevent its growth.

Key words: Antibacterial, *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus*.

INTRODUCTION

Soil biological activities occur by aerobic unicellular where small parts of these operations are conducted by anaerobic microorganisms which often reside in deep depths and layers. Aerobic microbes are gathered in upper layers of soil where humus and organic matters exist. Likewise, much value of oxygen is present in underground which demonstrates maximum of activity. It is much in number because of this layer where too many organisms are established and placed. With the reduction of oxygen and

organic matters from upper layers, activity and value of microorganisms fail in underground level. In biological definition of soil, we can assess biological activity through live creatures in soil. A part of biological activities in soil result from fungi. (Mc Laughlin, 2001). Microscopic fungi make its life activity apparent through spore. Their distribution is done through producing spore. With the rise of organic matters especially nitrogen in the environment they increase in number. Value of fungi in fertile arable lands is usually less than bacteria and actinomycetes and its environmental reaction is different depending on

different seasons of year. Their maximum value is usually observed in spring and fall. Most of them are resistant to dryness and can also do their operations in acid condition completely. Totally they are more in value in humid soil compared to semi-dry and dry areas. Among microscopic fungi some live in form of parasite and generating diseases and other ones live in saprophytes form on remaining of organic matters. Fungus of *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* are the most common ones which are found nearly in all areas of dry soil to humid area. (Alexopoulos, 1996). Soil bacteria are unicellular organisms with plan origin on which there is microscopic dimensions (1-10micron) and they can be compared with particles of clay. Adjacent to root of organic plants and in fresh organic matters, they grow more and can live much longer. Depending on value of soil they reach to 2 billion in each gram. Usually their value and activity depend on PH of environment. If the best reactive environment for bacteria is almost neutral, they can find good place for living in calcareous soils and soils where there is sufficient amount of cation and they are propagated fast. In order to investigate biology of soil it seems necessary to separate, identify and study each of microorganisms available in soil (Lotfi, 2010). In many biological and biochemical sources of soil, enzyme activities of soil are studied which can be applied as an index for measuring biological activity of soil. (Kossem, 1995).

Probably all the microorganism studies do have enzyme activity which caused to such conclusion. Separation and purifying secondary metabolic of soil and assessing them in soil is that hard. Hence, laboratory studies seem simple and valid in producing secondary metabolic applying pure culture. Among various secondary metabolic groups, biologists are into antibiotics as inhibitors of growth microorganism more than others. *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* fungi are main antibiotic producers which are able to produce and can influence on other microorganisms in different areas. (McLaughlin, 2001). Natural compounds were the most important sources of antibiotics or antibiotic prototypes in the past (Butler, 2006). Despite

wide expectations of syntheses molecules with effective antibiotic features, natural compounds still promise valuable factors. (Newman & Cragg, 2007). A research was done regarding new strains for microorganisms, but their antibiotic activities were not assessed yet which can produce new molecules or useful samples for developing antibiotics (Sofia & Boldi, 2006). Antibiotics produced were separated from microorganisms and most of different residents such as Plant Endophytic (Gunatilaka, 2006) and marine organisms (Gandhimathi, 2008). Microorganisms are so significant in soil for biochemical cycle, since they lead to biological changes in the environment. Qualitative and quantitative approaches of assessing fungi present in soil are described well (Rousk & Baath, 2007).

Too much fungi extractions and extracellular components were found with antimicrobial activity most of which were separated from filamentous *Penicillium* fungus. Since the discovery of *Penicillium* fungus are known as antibiotic producers and other secondary metabolic with biological activity.

Filamentous fungus *Penicillium* produces antibacterial matters in soil which can lead to removal of some bacteria in soil. In this research we dealt with the ability of production of antibacterial agents and prevention of gram-positive and negative bacteria growth which had been removed from Iran`s agricultural soils. Using isolate stimulation, we dealt with production of antibiotics by adding bacteria to fungus culture.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fungi and bacteria sued in this research were separated from soil of arable land of Iran and using key they were identified. Likewise, 5 isolates of *P chrysogenum* were bought from collection center of fungi and industrial bacteria of Iran.

First fungi were cultured in PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar) then spore suspension was prepared and the concentration of spores was

measured. For spore suspension preparation, fungi were cultured on PDA media and after fungal growth and spore production, 5 ml of sterile distilled water was added and was placed on the stirrer for 2 minutes to mix the spores with water. The number of spores was measured by a hemocytometer lam.

Bacteria were cultured in NAS (Nutrient Agar Sucrose) Media and after a week bacterial suspension with a certain concentration was prepared. Bacterial colony was added to the 1.5ml vials containing sterile distilled water then the concentration was adjusted with spectrophotometer.

For anti-bacterial test, potato dextrose broth (PDB) was prepared. Then these media were inoculated with bacterial and fungal spore suspensions. Samples were incubated at room temperature on a shaker with 120 rpm. Tests were performed in a three iteration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Among fungi studied, some samples showed significant results (Ekesi, 2005) indicating significant presence of metabolic in them which needs more investigation. Most of bacteria isolates used in this study are gram-negative bacteria which are plant pathogens.

Table-1. Bacterial and fungal cultures in broth media

Fungi	Bacteria			
	<i>P. viridiflava</i>	<i>X. campestris</i>	<i>R. iranicus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
<i>A. awamori</i>	---	+++	+++	---
<i>A. niveus</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>A. ferreus</i>	---	+++	+++	---
<i>A. usteus</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>A. sclerotiorum</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>A. ostianus</i>	---	+++	+++	---
<i>A. niger</i>	---	+++	+++	---
<i>A. corneus</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>A. fumigatus</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>A. parasitica</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>A. flavus</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>A. foetidus</i>	---	+++	+++	---
<i>P. moldavicum</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>P. mali</i>	---	+++	+++	---
<i>P. nigricans</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>P. piscarium</i>	---	---	---	---
<i>P. jenseii</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>P. janthinellum</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>P. corylophilum</i>	---	---	---	---
<i>P. cremeo-griseum</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>P. canescens</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>P. pinophilum</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>P. crustoseum</i>	---	+++	+++	---
<i>P. griseofulvum</i>	---	---	---	---
<i>P. chrysogenum</i>	---	---	---	---
<i>P. cammuni</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>P. aurantiigriseum</i>	---	---	+++	---
<i>P. citrinum</i>	---	+++	+++	---
<i>P. chrysogenum5031</i>	---	+++	+++	---
<i>P. chrysogenum5033</i>	+++	---	+++	---
<i>P. chrysogenum5037</i>	+++	+++	+++	---
<i>P. chrysogenum5071</i>	+++	+++	+++	---
<i>P. chrysogenum5074</i>	---	+++	+++	---

As you may observe in table 1, most of types were not capable of controlling bacteria *P. viridiflava*, except isolates of (5071, 5037 and 5033) from type *P. chrysogenum*. Regarding bacterium *R. iranicus* we can claim that only *P. piscarium*, *P. corylophilum*, *P. griseofulvum* and *P. chrysogenum* were not able to control this bacterium and other types produced metabolic which were able to control this bacterial and did not allow growing up. Bacteria *X. camstris py. Campestris* which is a key plant bacterial disease showed significant results. Following types were able to control this key bacterium: *P. chrysogenum* 5037, *P. chrysogenum* 5071, *P. chrysogenum* 5074, *A. foetidus*, *P. mali*, *P. crustoseum*, *P. citrinum*, *P. chrysogenum* 5031, *A. awamori*, *A. ferreus*, *A. ostianus* and *A. niger*. Regarding *E. coli* bacteria, none of fungi could control this bacterium. Maybe we can argue that the metabolic with ability of removing this bacterium was not produced which paved the way for easy growth of this bacterium. Based on the results mentioned we can argue that these fungi do have the ability of controlling some of the bacteria in soil. Since these bacteria produce diseases in plants, presence of these fungi in soil is important for reducing losses. Natural compounds with pharmaceutical uses, played an important role to treat human diseases and microbial environments are important sources of natural active agents (Newman D.J. et al. 2003). Many compounds that are commonly used in wide ranges are obtained by microbial fermentations or chemical modifications of biological compounds (Pranitha et al, 2014 and Donadio S. et al. 2002). In this context, fermentation is an efficient process for secondary metabolites production which could not be extracted from plants and animals and even could not be produced by genetic manipulations (Demain A.L. 2000). Two antibiotics with new antifungal properties were isolated from *Aspergillus fumigates* isolates (Mukhopadhyay T. et al. 1987). In an effort to find cell cycle inhibitors with microbial origins, diketopiperazin was isolated from culture fermentation of *A. fumigates* fungus (Cui C. B. et al. 1997). Mentioned substances may play a role in bacterial control of *Penicillium* species

tested in our experiments, which requires further investigations about these issues in the future.

Figure-1. Positive and negative results of broth media cultivation test, from right to left.

CONCLUSION

Part of the events that occur in the soil could be simulated at laboratory conditions. In this study, results indicated several species of *Penicillium* have the ability to control some plant pathogenic bacteria. Subsequent studies regarding beneficial and harmful metabolites of microorganisms could be promising.

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